

**EXPLORING SHARED HOUSING AS A SOLUTION TO
INTERGENERATIONAL HOMELESSNESS IN CAMDEN
COUNTY, NEW JERSEY**

By

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CAPSTONE ABSTRACT

Exploring Shared Housing as A Solution to Intergenerational Homelessness in Camden County, New Jersey

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This research addresses the urgent homelessness crisis in Camden, New Jersey, where a severe lack of affordable housing fuels intergenerational poverty. It investigates shared housing – a model involving unrelated individuals sharing a residence while maintaining private spaces – as a cost effective intervention capable of reducing housing assistance costs by up to 30%. The study employs a mixed-methods approach, analyzing existing shared housing models in Camden and similar urban contexts, while gathering stakeholder perspectives through interviews and surveys. Applying Housing First Model and Social Capital theories, this research identifies barriers to implementation, particularly landlord hesitation and community opposition. Anticipated results will demonstrate the potential of shared housing as a "prevention-as-cure" strategy, providing economic relief and psychosocial support for beneficiaries. This project will generate actionable policy recommendations, including a strategic landlord engagement program and initiatives to promote community acceptance. By advancing sustainable, upstream interventions, this work contributes to disrupting the cycle of intergenerational homelessness and promoting equity in Camden.

Dedication

To God.

To my daughter, Firefly.

To myself, for not giving up.

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President Barack Obama’s visionary leadership in launching the Mandela Washington Fellowship (MWF) for Young African Leaders shaped the trajectory of my career and brought me to the United States for the first time in 2016.

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CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background and Context

Homelessness remains the most visible and persistent form of urban poverty in Camden County, New Jersey. The Point-in-Time Count, (an annual one-night census of individuals and families experiencing homelessness within a specific geographic area), revealed 743 persons experiencing homelessness in Camden County in 2024. Camden City, a municipality within the county and home to Rutgers University and Cooper Hospital, contributed nearly 68% of this population. Of particular concern is the demographic composition of this population: 316 individuals are between the ages of 18 and 44, representing a vibrant group whose potential contributions to economic development are severely undermined by the destabilizing effects of homelessness. Alarming, only 2% of respondents at the 2024 Point-in-Time Count reported a last permanent address outside the county (Monarch Housing Associates, 2024), highlighting the local nature of the crisis.

One of the most critical challenges is the scarcity of affordable housing options for individuals at risk of homelessness. Between 2021 and 2023, the median rental price increased by \$450, while the median household income only rose by \$175 (Data USA, 2023). This is further contextualized by the U.S. Department of Housing and Urban Development's Fair Market Rents data, which underscores the growing affordability gap in Camden. These trends align with national data from the National Low Income Housing Coalition (2024), which indicates a severe shortage of affordable housing in New Jersey, with only 30 units available for every 100 families in need. A 2024 March Rent Report highlights that rental costs in New Jersey increased by 6.2% over the past year, further compounding the challenges for low-income residents.

1.2 Problem Statement

The convergence of rising rents, stagnant incomes, and a severe shortage of affordable housing paints a picture of the increasing vulnerability of Camden residents to homelessness. Yet despite the

growing urgency, Camden lacks scalable, preventative housing models that address both structural and relational dimensions of homelessness. In this context, traditional approaches to addressing homelessness, which often focus on reactive interventions, prove insufficient. The data highlights the urgent need for proactive, "prevention-as-cure" strategies that address the root causes of housing instability and mitigate the risk of homelessness before it occurs.

1.3 Purpose of the Study

This study explores shared housing as a sustainable, community-based intervention to prevent homelessness in Camden City. Shared housing, a housing arrangement involving the habitation and sharing of the cost of a single residence by unrelated individuals—each maintaining their private space while using shared common spaces such as kitchens, living rooms, and bathrooms—is emerging as an innovative solution to mitigate homelessness. By fostering collaborative living arrangements that maximize limited housing resources and promote community stability, shared housing can play a pivotal role in breaking the cycle of intergenerational homelessness.

1.4 Significance of the Study

This study contributes to growing scholarship on homelessness prevention by evaluating shared housing as a model that is both cost-effective and community-oriented. Although the Housing First model and shared housing programs have been extensively studied in larger metropolitan areas such as Los Angeles, New York and neighboring places like Philadelphia and Delaware, much less attention has been given to the role of shared housing in smaller, economically distressed urban centers like Camden City. Existing research focuses largely on traditional homelessness interventions, such as rapid rehousing or emergency shelters, without examining how proactive shared housing strategies could function as a scalable, preventative solution in low-income cities.

Also, the relationship between gentrification pressures, systemic racial disparities, and rising housing costs in Camden has not been sufficiently linked to homelessness prevention models in prior

literature.

By situating shared housing within Camden's unique structural and demographic challenges, this study addresses a critical space in the literature and provides evidence-based policy recommendations for other cities grappling with similar housing crises.

1.5 Research Question and Hypothesis

Main Research Question

In what ways might the implementation of shared housing initiatives disrupt the cycle of intergenerational homelessness in Camden City?

Sub-questions

1. What are the economic and social benefits of shared housing for individuals at risk of homelessness?
2. What factors contribute to landlord hesitancy and community opposition to shared housing?
3. What policy strategies encourage the adoption of shared housing in Camden?

Hypothesis

Implementation of shared housing initiatives (IV) is associated with improved housing stability and reduced homelessness (DV) among vulnerable populations in Camden City.

1.6 Research Aims and Objectives

Aim 1

The primary aim is to explore how shared housing initiatives may disrupt the cycle of intergenerational homelessness in Camden City. Adopting an exploratory approach, this research will investigate the mechanisms through which shared housing models—designed to offer cost-efficient living arrangements and essential psychosocial support—contribute to housing stability for vulnerable populations. Using a comparative approach, data will be analyzed from existing programs

and case studies across the United States. This research will also analyze existing programs in Camden County—such as the Senior Citizens United Community Services (SCUCS))—to assess how these models contribute to housing stability and improved economic outcomes for vulnerable populations.

Aim 2

The second aim is to identify and diagnose the key social, economic, and policy-related obstacles that hinder the broader acceptance and implementation of shared housing initiatives in Camden City. This objective will be achieved through a comprehensive analysis of stakeholder attitudes—including those of landlords, service providers, and community members—using qualitative interviews. By identifying barriers to participation and other systemic challenges, the study will lay the groundwork for developing evidence-based policy recommendations to facilitate wider adoption of shared housing as a sustainable solution to prevent homelessness.

1.7 Contextual Overview: SCUCS and Shared Housing in Camden

County

This research draws on Senior Citizens United Community Services (SCUCS) as a case study to understand the potential of shared housing in Camden. SCUCS is a nonprofit organization based in Camden County, New Jersey. Among its many services, SCUCS operates a longstanding Shared Housing Program designed to address both housing insecurity and social isolation among older adults. The program matches homeowners aged 60+ or those with physical disabilities with adults aged 21+ seeking affordable accommodation. It serves as a preventive solution for people at risk of homelessness who have low, but steady incomes.

By examining its intake process, stakeholder coordination, and outcomes, the study seeks to extract lessons that can inform broader implementation strategies for preventing homelessness through shared housing.

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Framing the Literature: Poverty, Urban Poverty, and Camden City as a Microcosm of Structural Inequality

Poverty, at its core, refers to a lack of access to essential resources such as housing, food, healthcare, and education. In urban contexts, however, poverty manifests in more complex forms. Urban poverty is not only financial deprivation but includes overcrowding, unemployment, racial segregation, and limited access to public services and infrastructure (Shinn & Khadduri, 2020).

According to the U.S. Department of Housing and Urban Development (HUD, 2019), homelessness is defined as the lack of a fixed, regular, and adequate nighttime residence, including those in shelters or in places not meant for habitation. Poverty and homelessness are closely linked, however they are distinct social problems. While not all individuals who live in poverty are homeless, nearly all individuals experiencing homelessness live in poverty.

National data show that homelessness has spiked significantly in recent years:

- In 2023, over 653,104 individuals were reported homeless, a 12.1% year-over-year increase (Security.org, 2024; USA Today, 2024).
- By 2024, this number rose to 771,400, an 18% increase from 2023 (Econofact, 2025; USA Today, 2024).

This indicates that homelessness in Camden City is not only a local crisis but a case study in how structural poverty, rising rents, and policy limitations converge to perpetuate housing insecurity. Building on the local context presented in Chapter One, this literature review explores how national trends, theoretical frameworks, and evidence-based models—particularly shared housing—help illuminate both the drivers of and potential solutions to homelessness in Camden.

Fig.1: 15 year Homeless Comparison in Camden County by Category (Monarch Housing, 2024)

2.2 Housing Affordability and Other Structural Drivers of Homelessness

Policy responses have largely focused on level and individualized causes of homelessness such as substance abuse or individual misfortune. This thesis adopts a Structural Inequality theory policy lens, which understands homelessness not as a consequence of individual failure, but as the outcome of systemic inequities and institutional gaps in housing access, labor markets, and social safety nets. Structural Inequality theory emphasizes that housing insecurity is deeply embedded in policies, power dynamics, and resource distribution (Shinn & Khadduri, 2020; Burt, 2001).

2.2.1 Income-Rent Disparities in Camden

The Homelessness crisis is exacerbated by rapidly rising rents. The average rent for an apartment in New Jersey reached \$2,523 in 2024—22% above the national average (NJ Spotlight News, 2025). Between 2021 and 2023, median rent in Camden rose by \$450, while the median household income rose by only \$175 (Data USA, 2023). In 2024 alone, rent rose an additional 6.2% (March Rent Report, 2024). This figure illustrates the upward trend in average monthly rent alongside fluctuations in homelessness rates in Camden City from 2020 through 2023. Rent data were sourced from Zillow’s Observed Rent Index (ZORI) for Camden, NJ (Zillow, 2024), while homelessness rates were obtained from the Camden County Point-in-Time Count reports (Monarch Housing Associates, 2024). The data suggest a correlation between rising housing costs and increased homelessness, highlighting the urgency of affordable housing interventions.

Recent analyses highlight the severity of the affordable housing shortage in New Jersey substantiating research about how policy decisions at federal, state, and local levels play a significant role in shaping the conditions that lead to homelessness. According to the Fair Share Housing Center (2024), the state faces a deficit of more than 230,000 affordable homes, with an estimated 14 prospective renters vying for every available affordable unit. With only 30 affordable units available for every 100 low-income renters in Camden many residents are priced out of stable housing (National Low Income Housing Coalition, 2024). Hence, the New Jersey Department of Community Affairs has identified a pressing need to restore or add thousands of affordable units to meet both current and future demand in Camden County (Fair Share Housing Center, 2024).

2.2.2 Policy Shortcomings and other Systemic Failures

Micro-level approaches often overlook robust evidence of the inverse correlation between incomes and rent costs, which renders housing unaffordable for low-income individuals and misrepresents the systemic nature of the crisis. Such approaches have contributed to

- i. the criminalization of homelessness
- ii. an overreliance on law enforcement interventions,
- iii. and the implementation of costly, often ineffective strategies—for example, requiring compliance with treatment programs as a precondition for accessing housing (Shinn & Khadduri, 2020; Burt, 2001).

Inadequacy of housing assistance funds has led to long waitlists and limited access to vouchers. In Camden County, the Tenant Based Rental Assistance (TBRA) program is often insufficient to cater to the needs of at-risk households, leaving many on waiting lists while also highlighting the urgency of the housing crisis. According to Affordable Housing Online (2024), 1,804 households with a Section 8 voucher in Camden County waited an average of 37 months to receive assistance., and only 90 households—just 5 percent— obtained a voucher in the past year through the Housing Authority of the City of Camden.

The Structural Inequality theory complements the Housing First approach, which views housing as a prerequisite for stability (Tsemberis, 2010) and enables us address homelessness through socially supportive upstream interventions like shared housing.

Median Rental Price over Time

In the last year, rent has increased by \$450 compared to the previous year.

Fig.2: Camden City Rental Data (Zillow Rentals,2024)

Studies by Parolin (2023) and Center on Budget and Policy Priorities (2024) found that increasing access to as Temporary Assistance for Needy Families (TANF) a federally funded program that provides cash assistance to eligible low-income families with children access could significantly reduce student and family homelessness. pointing to the need for targeted cash assistance rather than broad poverty reduction efforts alone. However, many states maintain restrictive eligibility requirements TANF the program limiting access for the people who need it most.

2.3 Race, Segregation and Systemic Injustice

Demographic data from Camden County's 2024 Point-in-Time Count reveals severe racial disparities in homelessness. In 2021, it was reported that 42% of Black families and 48% of Hispanic families in Camden experienced housing insecurity, compared to 22% of white families (New Jersey Homelessness Prevention Task Force, 2021). Furthermore, Black and African American residents have significantly overrepresented compared to their share of the general population This is especially striking given that Black or African American residents make up about 41% of the

population, and Hispanic or Latino residents comprise approximately 54% of Camden City, (Neilsberg, 2025; New Jersey Demographics, 2025).

- Black and Latino families face higher eviction rates and lower access to quality housing (Olivet et al., 2021)
- Discrimination in education and credit access, zoning, and employment limits long-term mobility

Fig 3: Number of persons by Race (Monarch Housing, 2024)

Systemic barriers concentrate poverty in marginalized communities and limit upward mobility, perpetuating cycles of housing instability and homelessness. This aligns with national trends, where minority populations are often overrepresented among those experiencing homelessness (Olivet et al., 2021). According to Monarch Housing (2024), the chart below “highlights that race rather than poverty appears to be a more predictive indicator of who will experience homelessness”.

These result in far reaching consequences. As housing costs outpace wages, families are forced into

overcrowded units, temporary shelters, or onto the streets.

Racial disparities in housing are not incidental—they are embedded in structural arrangements that perpetuate unequal outcomes. Without addressing these root causes, racial equity in housing will remain elusive.

2.4 Gentrification and Displacement in Camden

Applying Neil Smith's (1979) rent gap theory—which suggests that gentrification is driven by the disparity between a property's current value and its potential value after reinvestment—helps explain the dynamics of urban redevelopment, gentrification and displacement in downtown Camden. Several years of disinvestment and the demolition of low-income housing, suppressed property values, reduced the tax base, creating a significant rent gap. As reinvestment increase in the city through expansion of institutions like Rutgers University–Camden and Cooper Health System, it has contributed to rising property values and attracted more affluent residents and businesses (Danley & Weaver, 2018). These redevelopment efforts present a double-edged sword. While bringing positive changes in infrastructure and services, it also raises concerns about displacement and housing insecurity among vulnerable populations. It also risks displacing long-time, low-income residents.

Local reporting documents widespread fears among Camden residents that new investment may lead to exclusion or displacement, even when direct displacement risk is low (Shelterforce, 2020) This resistance reflects concerns about displacement and loss of community identity. (Pew Charitable Trusts, 2016, Danley & Weaver, 2018).

While gentrification is not the sole cause of homelessness, its role in amplifying housing insecurity among already at-risk populations is evident in Camden, where over 36% of the population lives below the federal poverty line (U.S. Census Bureau, 2021), displacement due to rising housing costs can push precariously housed individuals and families into homelessness.

2.5 Lived Realities of At-Risk Populations in Camden City

While statistical data illustrates the magnitude of homelessness in Camden City, it does not reflect the lived experiences of individuals navigating housing instability daily. Research documents that many at-risk residents experience "hidden homelessness," living in vehicles, staying temporarily with family or friends, or staying in abandoned buildings (Monarch Housing Associates, 2024; Camden County Homeless Trust Fund Task Force, 2023).

In Camden, families may "double up"—sharing limited space with extended relatives in unsafe and overcrowded conditions—while single adults and young people increasingly face periods of street homelessness or unsafe housing arrangements (Regional Plan Association, 2023). Unstable living conditions cause chronic stress, disrupt access to healthcare and education, and often prevent stable employment, thereby reinforcing the cycle of poverty. In fact, being asked to leave a shared residence and the risk of eviction were the two highest causes of homelessness in Camden County in 2024. marginalization (National Alliance to End Homelessness, 2024, Monarch Housing 2024).

Fig. 4: Factors Causing or Contributing to Homelessness in Camden County (Monarch Housing, 2024)

Recognizing and addressing these lived realities is crucial for developing housing interventions that are not only affordable but also socially supportive and culturally responsive. Shared housing models, as discussed later in this thesis, offer a pathway to restoring both physical shelter and social belonging for individuals facing chronic housing instability.

2.6 The intergenerational Nature of Homelessness: A Call for Urgent Interventions

Evidence consistently shows that homelessness, especially when first experienced in childhood, significantly increases the risk of repeat episodes later in life, perpetuating a cycle of poverty and instability. 43% of individuals who experienced homelessness once had a recurrent episode within six years. (McQuiston et al., 2014). Further research demonstrates that adults who experienced homelessness as children report higher rates of Adverse Childhood Experiences (ACEs), which are strongly linked to poor educational, social, and health outcomes (Cutuli & Willard, 2016; Fisher & Gilliam, 2012; Harris & Kalomas, 2018).

Fig. 5: Intergenerational Poverty Cycle

Figure five shows how these disruptions affects children’s ability to acquire education and skills for future livelihoods and also their capacity to maintain stable employment and social support networks as adults. Under the McKinney-Vento Homeless Assistance Act, the 2022-2023 school year reported that more than 1.2 million students nationwide experienced homelessness, a number

that has remained consistently high over the past decade (U.S. Department of Education, 2023). Many of these students are returning, not new, entries—indicating that homelessness is not always short-lived. These children face barriers to learning, social development, and long-term housing security—conditions that increase their risk of becoming homeless adults.

Local data from Camden City reinforce these national trends. In 2024, more than 300 young adults were recorded as homeless and 34.7% of homeless households experienced multiple episodes of homelessness within one year. (Monarch Housing Associates, 2024). This reality call for prioritizing urgent and comprehensive preventative interventions. Stabilizing families through early support, housing assistance, and trauma-informed services before homelessness occurs can disrupt this cycle and provide both children and adults the foundation they need to thrive.

Fig. 6: Homeless Population by Race (Monarch Housing, 2024)

2.7 Shared Housing: A Prevention as Cure Strategy for Homelessness

Shared Housing is a living arrangement where individuals, often unrelated, share a residence to reduce living costs and create a supportive environment. This setup can involve a variety of formats, such as co-living spaces where residents have private rooms but share common areas (e.g., kitchens, bathrooms, and living rooms) or more integrated arrangements like roommates or families sharing a home. (National Alliance to End Homelessness, 2020; HUD Exchange, 2021)

This initiative reduces the rent burden on individuals by allowing multiple residents to split housing costs, including rent, utilities, and maintenance expenses. By dividing these costs among several people, each individual's financial load becomes significantly lighter, making housing more affordable. This arrangement is particularly beneficial in low-income areas where securing independent Housing might be financially unfeasible for vulnerable residents.

In Camden, shared housing programs like those run by Senior Citizens United Community Services (SCUCS) and the Volunteers of America show great promise but have remained underutilized. These programs offer reduced rent and built-in social support. However, their growth is hindered by zoning restrictions, and landlord hesitancy. In states like California and Colorado, shared housing initiatives have been scaled with the support of public-private partnerships and centralized coordination offices (Byrne et al., 2021)

As demonstrated throughout this chapter, homelessness is not merely a personal crisis but a systemic failure rooted in housing unaffordability. Shared housing emerges as a cost-effective, community-based intervention that directly addresses this. If prevention is truly better than cure, then shared housing is the policy prescription Camden should embrace.

Shared housing is often mistakenly conflated with rooming or boarding houses, but the two are fundamentally different in design, governance, and intent. While rooming houses involve multiple unrelated tenants renting individual rooms in a commercially managed property—often with limited say in household governance—shared housing, as examined in this thesis, emphasizes mutual consent, relational compatibility, and cohabitation with shared responsibilities. Unlike rooming houses, shared housing typically involves homeowners voluntarily renting out part of their residence, with arrangements tailored to each match and often supported by nonprofit coordination (SCUCS Interview, 2025). Recognizing this distinction is crucial for designing appropriate policies, zoning exemptions, and public messaging strategies that support community-based housing solutions without invoking the stigma or regulatory complexity associated with rooming houses.

2.7.1 Income Eligibility

A crucial yet often overlooked component of shared housing programs is income eligibility. While shared housing reduces the cost of living, it still assumes a baseline income on the part of the home seeker. For instance, SCUCS requires that participants have a reliable monthly income and that rental contributions do not exceed half of their earnings. This approach promotes affordability and long-term housing stability but also excludes individuals with no income or irregular earnings—highlighting the need for hybrid models or supplementary support for Camden’s most vulnerable populations.

2.7.2 Landlord Engagement: The Missing Link in Shared Housing

One of the most significant barriers to the success of shared housing initiatives is the reluctance of landlords to rent to individuals using tenant-based rental assistance (TBRA), such as Section 8 vouchers. In Camden, this hesitation often stems from fears of delayed payments, property damage, or tenant instability. This reflects broader stigmas against low-income renters (Fair Share Housing Center, 2024). Without landlord buy-in, shared housing programs will not be efficient or implementable due to a lack of available units.

Neighboring cities like Philadelphia and Delaware have implemented landlord incentive programs that offer signing bonuses, damage mitigation funds, and guaranteed rent payments. These incentives have proven to reverse these trends of landlord apathy and offer promising lessons for Camden. (Philadelphia Office of Homeless Services, 2023). Furthermore, providing landlords with training programs on shared housing best practices, conflict resolution, and legal protections can build trust and support program growth.

A centralized coordination office in Camden with a dedicated liaison officer could serve as a single point of contact between landlords, service providers, and housing authorities. This would offer landlords a consistent and supportive experience.

2.8 Synthesis and Conclusion

The literature reviewed across structural, racial, generational, and policy dimensions affirms that homelessness in Camden is deeply rooted in affordability gaps, racialized housing policies, and intergenerational disadvantage. Traditional reactive approaches such as shelters and policing have failed to address the structural causes that push residents into homelessness in the first place. By contrast, shared housing, presents a practical, community-driven intervention that addresses both economic and psychosocial needs. Its potential to lower housing costs, stabilize families, and reduce demand on strained public systems makes it an essential model for consideration. If prevention is better than cure, Camden's path to functional zero homelessness may actually depend on its willingness to scale models like shared housing that prevent homelessness before it begins.

CHAPTER THREE: METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

This study employs a mixed-methods exploratory design which integrates qualitative and quantitative approaches to investigate how shared housing initiatives can serve as a preventative strategy against homelessness in Camden City. The research begins with qualitative data collection and analysis to capture stakeholder perspectives, followed by quantitative data collection to contextualize structural trends such as housing affordability and homelessness rates. This sequential design allows for a nuanced understanding of both systemic factors and individual realities, consistent with Creswell and Creswell's (2018) recommendations for mixed-methods research.

The study is framed within a Structural Inequality theory perspective, which views homelessness as a systemic issue rooted in political, economic, and social structures rather than individual failings. Given the frequent conflation of shared housing with rooming houses in public discourse, this study clarifies that shared housing refers to a living arrangement where unrelated individuals share a home with private bedrooms but common living spaces, often with a focus on mutual support and affordability, whereas rooming housing typically involves renting individual rooms in a property with less emphasis on shared responsibilities or social connection among tenants. This distinction helps establish a clear conceptual framework guiding the research.

3.2 Theoretical Framework

This study is grounded in a Structural Inequality theory policy perspective, which recognizes that homelessness is fundamentally a result of systemic inequalities rather than solely individual failings.

Two complementary theoretical frameworks underpin this study: -

The Housing First Model: (Tsemberis, 2010) posits that stable housing is a requirement for addressing other challenges such as employment or health. This model advocates for immediate housing placement without preconditions, emphasizing housing stability as the foundation for

recovery and self-sufficiency.

The Structural Inequality theory: (Byrne, Henwood, & Orlando, 2021) conceptualize homelessness as the outcome of systemic inequities, including discriminatory housing policies, exclusionary zoning, racial wealth gaps, and inadequate wage protections. Applying this lens to Camden City enables a critical examination of how historical disinvestment, gentrification, and racial disparities contribute to housing insecurity, highlighting the limitations of emergency-focused responses. Together, these frameworks position shared housing as a strategic structural intervention aimed at preventing homelessness by addressing upstream causes and promoting housing stability.

3.3 Research Questions, Objectives, and Hypotheses

This study seeks to answer the following research questions and test the associated hypotheses, as introduced in Chapter 1, and framed within the Housing First and Structural Inequality frameworks discussed above.

Main Research Question

- In what ways might the implementation of shared housing initiatives disrupt the cycle of intergenerational homelessness in Camden City?

Sub-Questions

1. What are the economic and social benefits of shared housing for individuals at risk of homelessness?
2. What factors contribute to landlord hesitancy and community opposition to shared housing?
3. What policy strategies encourage the adoption and successful implementation of shared housing initiatives in Camden?

Research Hypothesis

- **H1:** The implementation of shared housing initiatives (Independent Variable) is associated with improved housing stability and reduced homelessness (Dependent Variable) among at-risk populations in Camden City.

Research Objectives

- To explore the mechanisms through which shared housing contributes to housing stability for at-risk individuals.
- To identify and analyze the social, economic, and policy barriers hindering shared housing implementation in Camden.
- To propose evidence-based policy recommendations that promote shared housing as a sustainable solution to preventing homelessness.

Each of these research questions, objectives, and hypotheses is directly tied to the problem statement outlined in Chapter 1 and the gaps in prior research discussed in Chapter 2, ensuring a consistent and structured research design. The following section outlines the data sources and collection methods used to gather relevant information.

3.4 Variables and Measurement

This study integrates secondary quantitative data and primary qualitative insights to address the research questions.

- **Independent Variable:** Shared housing interventions (e.g., participation in programs like SCUCS).
- **Dependent Variable:** Housing stability outcomes, operationalized through indicators such as duration of housing retention, reduction in shelter use, and client reported housing security.

Construct	Measure(s)	Source
Housing Instability	Number of individuals experiencing homelessness	Point-in-Time (PIT) Count, 2024
Housing Affordability	Median rent compared to median household income	Zillow Rental Data (2025), Regional Plan Association (2023), Data USA (2023)
Effectiveness of Shared Housing	Number of matches made; program growth over time	SCUCS Interview (2025)
Landlord/Provider Engagement	Number of homeowners participating in SCUCS shared housing	SCUCS Interview (2025)
Socioeconomic Disparities	Median household income by race, rent burden percentages	U.S. Census Bureau (2024); Regional Plan Association (2023)

Table 1: Measurement Constructs and Data Sources

3.4.1 Quantitative Measures

- Homelessness Statistics: The 2024 Point-in-Time (PIT) Count by Monarch Housing Associates provides county-level data on homelessness prevalence and demographics.
- Rental Market Trends: Zillow Rental Index (2025) and Regional Plan Association reports (2023) supply data on rent prices, median incomes, and housing cost burdens.
- Income Levels: U.S. Census Bureau (2024) data contextualizes economic conditions in Camden.

3.4.2 Qualitative Measures

- Semi-structured interviews with SCUCS leadership and staff explore program operations, barriers, and success factors.
- Thematic coding of interview transcripts aligns with research objectives, focusing on social acceptance, economic benefits, and policy challenges.

3.5 Sampling and Ethical Considerations

- The qualitative sample consists of purposively selected SCUCS program staff and stakeholders with direct knowledge of shared housing operations.
- No direct interviews were conducted with persons experiencing homelessness due to ethical and logistical constraints.

Prior research supports the use of these measures. The PIT Count is an annual HUD-recognized tool for tracking homelessness trends. Rental cost and income data from Zillow, Data USA, and the U.S. Census Bureau are commonly used in housing affordability studies (Horowitz et al., 2023). Similarly, program data from nonprofit stakeholders like SCUCS offer validated, real-world evidence of shared housing impacts (Henwood et al., 2015; Johnson et al., 2018).

3.6 Construction of Measures

3.6.1 Primary Data

- Semi-structured interviews were conducted with SCUCS leadership via recorded sessions and manual note-taking.
- Interview guides were developed based on research questions and theoretical frameworks.

3.6.2 Secondary Data

- Data sources include Camden County PIT Count reports, Zillow rental data, Regional Plan Association and U.S. Census Bureau publications, and program documentation from SCUCS.
- Additional literature on shared housing, gentrification, and homelessness informed contextual understanding.

3.7 Data Analysis Methods

3.7.1 Qualitative Analysis

Interview transcripts were coded thematically by hand. The researcher systematically reviewed the

transcripts, highlighted recurring concepts, and organized them into themes such as community resistance, financial accessibility, client-centered matching, operational challenges, and evidence of long-term success

Themes were mapped to research objectives to assess barriers and facilitators of shared housing.

Five key themes emerged:

- **Community Resistance and Stigma**

SCUCS identified need for privacy, the individualistic nature of most Americans, and differences in township-level support/regulations as significant barriers. This highlights the need for community education and targeted landlord engagement strategies. It also supports the research objective of diagnosing barriers to shared housing acceptance.

- **Financial Accessibility and Economic Benefits**

Rents are capped at \$700 per month significantly reducing costs for home-seekers. Home providers often charge even less in exchange for companionship. This supports the research hypothesis that shared housing improves housing stability by reducing financial burdens.

- **Flexibility and Client-Centered Matching**

The use of personalized interviews, trial periods, and individually tailored contracts reflects a client-centered model. SCUCS's approach aligns with Housing First principles, emphasizing housing stability over rigid compliance requirements.

- **Operational Sustainability Challenges**

SCUCS faces marketing and funding gaps that limit program expansion. While word-of-mouth and relationship-building with local officials have helped, systemic support (e.g., dedicated advertising budgets) is lacking — This demonstrates gaps the thesis aims to address in policy recommendations.

- **Evidence of Long-Term Success:**

Case studies revealed shared housing matches lasting over 7–15 years, illustrating that

when properly managed, shared housing can offer durable, life-changing solutions directly supporting the research aim of evaluating shared housing's effectiveness.

3.7.2 Quantitative Context: Housing Instability and Affordability in Camden City

- Secondary data on homelessness prevalence, rental affordability, and income disparities were descriptively analyzed to contextualize Camden’s housing crisis.
- Comparative cost data for shared housing versus traditional interventions were synthesized from national reports.

Together, these indicators paint a comprehensive picture of the structural forces driving housing instability for vulnerable residents.

Indicator	Value	Source
Homeless population (2024 PIT)	743 individuals	Monarch Housing Associates, 2024
Average rent (2025)	\$1,600/month	Zillow Rental Data, 2025
Median renter income	\$20,804/year	Regional Plan Association, 2023
Rent as % of renter income	84%	Calculated
% renters cost-burdened (>50%)	65.6%	Regional Plan Association, 2023
Median household income (Camden City)	\$40,450	Point2Homes, 2023
Median household income (Camden County)	\$86,384	Neilsberg, 2023
Shared housing cost (annual)	\$12,775–\$18,250	National Alliance to End Homelessness, 2022
Emergency shelter cost (annual)	\$49,640	Community Solutions, 2023

Table 2: Summary of Key Quantitative indicators

This mixed-methods design enables a comprehensive exploration of shared housing as a preventative homelessness strategy in Camden City. Qualitative insights provide depth on stakeholder experiences and program dynamics, while quantitative data situates these findings within broader structural trends. Together, these methods support evidence-based policy recommendations to enhance shared housing implementation.

CHAPTER FOUR: FINDINGS

4.1 Shared Housing: A Strategic and Participatory Solution to Homelessness in Camden

The comparative cost analysis (see Table 4) demonstrates that while rapid rehousing and permanent supportive housing are both considerably less expensive than emergency shelters, hospitalization, or incarceration, the financial burden of all these interventions falls almost entirely on government and public funding streams (National Alliance to End Homelessness, 2025; Community Solutions, 2023). In contrast, shared housing models like that implemented by Senior Citizens United Community Services (SCUCS) in Camden County offer a more fiscally responsible and socially sustainable approach by shifting the primary cost of housing from taxpayers to co-participating residents.

Service Type	Cost per Person per Day (USD)	Cost per Person per Year (USD)	Source
Shared Housing (SCUCS Estimate)	\$23–\$24	\$8,400–\$8,760	Housing 4 the Homeless, 2024; SCUCS interview, 2025
Rapid Re-Housing	\$23	\$8,486	National Alliance to End Homelessness, 2025
Permanent Supportive Housing	\$55	\$20,115	National Alliance to End Homelessness, 2025
Emergency Shelter	\$136	\$49,640	Community Solutions, 2023
Incarceration (e.g., Rikers)	\$1,414	\$516,110	Community Solutions, 2023
Hospitalization (Homeless)	\$3,609	\$1,317,285	Community Solutions, 2023

Table 3. Comparative Cost Analysis of Homelessness Interventions by Service Type (2023-2025)

This cost differential provides a strategic avenue for policy reallocation. These savings could be redirected toward long-term prevention and structural reforms that address housing supply, affordability, and neighborhood revitalization.

4.2 Limitations of Existing Interventions in Camden

4.2.1 Policy Limitations

Camden’s public housing system is severely overburdened, characterized by long waitlists, limited voucher availability, and persistent landlord hesitancy that undermine access to stable housing. The 2024 Point-in-Time Count by Monarch Housing Associates identified government waitlists as the most significant barrier to housing services, with 96 households citing it as their primary obstacle—more than any other factor. Complementing this, data from Affordable Housing Online (2024) reveals that only 90 households—approximately 5%—were successfully placed with a Section 8 voucher last year, while 1,804 households remained on waiting lists, often for as long as 37 months. Even when vouchers are awarded, applicants frequently encounter further barriers such as income verification delays, credit screening, and rental discrimination, which hinder their ability to secure housing despite eligibility. These systemic obstacles contribute directly to the persistence and growth of homelessness in Camden.

Fig. 7: Number of Homeless Households by Barriers to Services

SCUCS has demonstrated how community partnerships and relationship-building can succeed where institutional programs fail. With flexible eligibility and low barrier entry, shared housing accelerates housing placements, bypasses the bottlenecks of subsidy-based programs, and increases system flow by enabling multiple individuals to access housing simultaneously (National Alliance to End Homelessness, 2022). Since 2019, SCUCS has grown from 5 home providers to 73 by April 2025. The organization has made 134 introductions and facilitated 39 successful matches, representing a 30% success rate.

4.2.2 Addressing Camden’s High Vacancy Rate through Shared Housing

A significant limitation of existing housing programs in Camden City is their inability to maximize the existing high rate of vacant housing units, which represents a substantial waste of valuable resources amidst a persistent housing crisis (Camden Housing Authority, 2024; HUD User, 2024). According to recent data, Camden County’s vacancy rate has increased over time, with thousands of units remaining unoccupied even as many residents struggle to find affordable housing (New Jersey Department of Labor, 2000 Census; Pew Charitable Trusts, 2024). This mismatch between available housing and community need highlights inefficiencies in current policy and program implementation.

Vacant units contributes both to neighborhood decline and lost economic potential, but also reflect an underutilization of the city’s existing housing stock (HUD, 2024). Rather than focusing solely on new construction or lengthy redevelopment plans, shared housing offers a strategic solution to maximize these existing resources. By facilitating arrangements where unrelated individuals share underused homes or apartments, shared housing can quickly and cost-effectively bring vacant or under-occupied units back into productive use, increasing affordable housing options without the delays and expenses of building new units (Home for All San Mateo County, n.d.; Pew Charitable Trusts, 2024).

4.3 Key Findings from SCUCS Implementation

The interview with SCUCS staff revealed both the promises and the barriers to the implementation of shared housing in Camden. The organization's greatest challenges are marketing, community stigma, and municipal variation—some townships are welcoming while others require bureaucratic navigation.

SCUCS staff emphasized that cultural factors in American society (individualism), exacerbated by the COVID-19 pandemic, fosters skepticism making it harder to market shared housing. Funding constraints have also limited their ability to advertise or expand rapidly. Town-by-town regulations vary widely, with some municipalities being supportive (e.g., Pennsauken) and others requiring more formal negotiation (e.g., Lindenwold). Major barriers include zoning restrictions, landlords' fears about property rights (e.g., adverse possession), low public awareness, and minimal funding for marketing and education efforts.

Despite operating with limited staff and funding, SCUCS continues to innovate in ways that maximize impact. Their outreach strategy is highly relational: staff actively engage community members by speaking at Rotary clubs, senior centers, tax offices, and local events to build trust and awareness. The intake and participant matching process is both thorough and low-barrier. Applicants complete intake forms and provide references, and SCUCS conducts informal interviews and background checks to ensure compatibility and safety. Once a match is made, each arrangement is governed by a customized, month-to-month home sharing contract that outlines responsibilities and protects homeowners from legal risks such as adverse possession. Beyond placement, SCUCS offers ongoing support services, including regular follow-up calls, conflict resolution, budgeting assistance, and incident reporting. These scaffolding mechanisms not only ensure stability but also foster a culture of accountability and care.

The SCUCS model proves that with adequate support and relationship-building, shared housing is viable, safe, and scalable—especially when targeted at seniors, low-income workers, and those on

public housing waitlists.

4.4 Argument for Policy Adoption and Expansion

If SCUCS—a single, under-resourced nonprofit—can match nearly 40 people and grow its provider base by more than 1,000% in six years, what could happen if multiple organizations embraced this model? The answer is clear: fewer individuals would fall through the cracks, more homes would be occupied, and fewer taxpayer dollars would be spent on costly stopgaps.

These evidence calls for the adoption of shared housing as part of Camden County’s housing strategy. With proper funding, municipal cooperation, and a public awareness campaign, shared housing could help the city move meaningfully toward zero homelessness by 2030.

4.5 Conclusion

This chapter has shown that shared housing is not simply a cheaper alternative but also a smarter, more humane, and participatory response to Camden’s housing crisis. SCUCS’ experience also demonstrates that when more homeowners participate, more matches occur, ultimately expanding affordable housing options.

CHAPTER FIVE: DISCUSSION, POLICY IMPLICATIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Overview and Summary of Key Findings

This chapter synthesizes the main findings of the study, critically discusses their implications for policy and practice, and presents actionable recommendations for Camden City. The analysis draws on both quantitative trends—such as the strong correlation between rising rents and increasing homelessness rates (see Figure 7 below)—and qualitative insights from stakeholders. The evidence demonstrates that shared housing, when strategically implemented, can address both the immediate crisis of homelessness and its structural drivers, including unaffordability, racial disparities, and

intergenerational poverty.

Figure 5.1 Camden City: Trends in Average Rent and Homelessness Rates, 2020–2023

Rent data: Zillow Observed Rent Index (2024); Homelessness data: Monarch Housing Associates, Camden County Point-in-Time Count (2024)

The chart above illustrates that as average rent in Camden City rose from \$938 in 2020 to \$1,411 in 2023, the homelessness rate also increased, particularly after 2021 when the COVID 19 moratorium expired, removing key protection from renters who lost income during the pandemic. This trend underscores the link between rent and income while also highlighting the urgent need for affordable, innovative housing solutions.

5.2 Policy Implications: Reframing Homelessness Prevention

The findings of this study reinforce that homelessness in Camden is not merely a result of individual failings but is fundamentally a structural issue rooted in housing unaffordability, poverty, systemic racial disparities, and disinvestment. As established in Chapter Two, over 65% of Camden renters are cost-burdened, and the city’s rent-to-income gap is among the widest in New Jersey (Regional Plan Association, 2023).

Shared housing emerges as a cost-effective, scalable intervention that reduces the financial burden of housing and enables rapid placements without requiring large-scale capital investments. Unlike

emergency shelters or traditional subsidies, that rely heavily on government funding and take years to process, shared housing places the cost-sharing responsibility among individuals while fostering social connection and mutual support. Shared housing requires robust stakeholder cooperation—including landlords, municipalities, nonprofits, and community members—to succeed. The evidence shows that when government funding is available, households can be quickly matched to shared or subsidized housing. However, funding inconsistencies and landlord hesitancy often disrupt these placements, perpetuating the crisis. Several of at risk persons have found shelter through SCUCS shared housing that provides a low-cost buffer regardless of government fiscal cycles. (SCUCS Interview, 2025).

5.3 Recommendations

To increase the scalability of shared housing in Camden County, a comprehensive approach focusing on landlord engagement, centralized coordination, and public awareness is essential. This strategy builds upon successful efforts of local nonprofits like Senior Citizens United Community Services while also incorporating evidence-based practices from Housing First programs.

5.3.1 Create a Coordinated Shared Housing Infrastructure

A key strategy for overcoming this challenge is the creation of a dedicated office for shared housing in Camden. This office would serve as a central hub for landlords, tenants, and service providers, streamlining communication and coordination. It would provide landlords with valuable resources, including information on financial incentives, legal protections, and the benefits of partnering with nonprofit organizations. Additionally, the office could offer roommate-matching services to facilitate tenant pairings, making it easier for landlords to find suitable tenants and reduce concerns about compatibility or potential issues.

Taking cue from Philadelphia’s catchy acronym **SHARE**, which stands for Shared Housing and Resource Exchange, Camden’s shared housing initiative should adopt a clear and resonant name

(such as CHIP – Camden Housing Integration Program or Camden SHARE – Shared Housing and Affordable Residency Expansion). As evidenced by Philadelphia SHARE program’s memorable name, the branding should effectively communicate its mission to connect homeowners and home seekers, making the concept accessible and easy to recall.

The role of the central coordination office includes but is not limited to :

- Standardizing intake procedures and home-matching protocols
- Managing outreach and recruitment of home providers
- Facilitate training for staff and participants
- Developing and implementing public education campaigns to build trust and reduce stigma

5.3.2: Prioritize Vulnerable Groups: Single Adults and Youth Aging Out of Foster

Care

Focusing on specific vulnerable groups allows Camden County to design and test shared housing programs tailored to the majority of those experiencing homelessness locally. Based on the 2024 Point-in-Time Count, 90% of homeless households in Camden County are adult-only, (Monarch Housing Associates, 2024). Additionally, youth aging out of foster care represent a high-risk group, with studies showing that 31% to 46% will experience homelessness by age 26 (Sevita Blog, 2025; US Interagency Council on Homelessness, 2023). By initially targeting these two groups, Camden can pilot shared housing interventions, gather key insights, and refine implementation strategies before scaling up.

To enhance the precision and efficiency of these efforts, Camden must also adopt data-driven targeting strategies. Local agencies already collect extensive data through Medicaid, TANF, Housing Choice Voucher applications, and eviction court records. Predictive models and integrated data systems—successfully applied in Los Angeles and New York—have proven effective in identifying those at greatest risk of housing loss (von Wachter et al., 2019; Collinson & Reed, 2017).

Additionally, researchers recommend tracking landlords with high eviction rates to flag neighborhoods where early intervention is most needed (Rutan & Desmond, 2021). By combining demographic targeting with predictive analytics, Camden can proactively reach residents on the brink—offering support before homelessness begins.

5.3.3 Implement Landlord Incentives and Legal Safeguards

Landlord hesitancy remains a major barrier to scaling shared housing. TO address this issue, Camden County should

Offering targeted education programs and provide legal templates for home-sharing agreements: The county should offer comprehensive training programs for landlords that address common concerns, such as tenant-landlord laws, conflict resolution, and property management for multiple tenants. These programs should also clarify the legal distinctions between tenancy and adverse possession, helping landlords understand their rights and responsibilities under lease agreements. Delaware’s Home Sharing Program has shown that partnering with legal aid offices and clearly distinguishing home-sharing from standard tenancy law can increase provider participation and security.

Provide incentives for participation: Financial incentives, similar to the Philadelphia OHS Landlord Incentive and Delaware State Housing Authority’s Landlord Incentive Program have shown financial incentives is associated with increased landlord engagement. This could include signing bonuses for landlords who participate in shared housing, along with guaranteed rent payments through programs like Housing Choice Vouchers (HCV). In addition, offering protections against rental income loss during delays or property damage could further reduce landlords' reluctance. Other strategies include Offer insurance subsidies or tax breaks to participating homeowners and enact municipal zoning reforms to allow accessory dwelling units (ADUs) and multi-occupancy use.

These steps will reassure providers, protect homeowners, and facilitate broader implementation without significant infrastructure development.

5.3.4 Use Shared Housing as Transitional Support

With voucher waitlists averaging 37 months in Camden County (Affordable Housing Online, 2024), shared housing should be positioned as transitional housing for those awaiting permanent placement. SCUCS already serves many individuals using shared housing as a stopgap between homelessness and independent living.

By investing in this model, Camden can reduce shelter demand, accelerate housing flow, and offer more agency to at-risk residents during their housing search.

5.3.5 Scale Low-Barrier Intake and Matching Models

Adopt SCUCS' low-barrier approach across Camden, which includes informal interviews, background checks, and preference matching. This model:

- Promotes trust and dignity,
- Protects vulnerable residents (especially the elderly and disabled),
- Increases match success and sustainability.

Philadelphia's SHARE Program, with a match retention rate above 70%, demonstrates the effectiveness of compatibility-focused matching.

5.3.6 Normalize Shared Housing Through Public Messaging

Public skepticism, often rooted in cultural norms and privacy concerns, can limit uptake. Hence, Camden should:

- Highlight positive stories from SCUCS and SHARE participants,
- Use trusted community voices (pastors, mayors, case managers),
- Dispel myths about "stranger danger" by focusing on safety protocols and mutual consent.

5.3.7 Use Shared Housing as Transitional Support During Voucher Wait Times

Given that voucher wait times in Camden can reach 37 months (Affordable Housing Online, 2024), shared housing should be promoted as a “bridge” solution. Evidence from SCUCS shows that many participants use shared housing while awaiting permanent placements, often transitioning to independent living once stabilized.

5.4 Limitations of the Study

While this research contributes to the growing body of knowledge on homelessness prevention, several limitations must be acknowledged:

- **Lack of lived experience voices:** No direct interviews with people currently or formerly experiencing homelessness or home sharing were conducted. Firsthand accounts would provide deeper insights.
- **Scope of case studies:** The focus is primarily on Camden County, with comparative references to Philadelphia and Delaware. Results may differ in other contexts.
- **Generalizability:** Shared housing programs vary in design and target populations; findings from SCUCS may not apply to all groups (e.g., families with children, youth aging out of foster care).

5.5 Conclusion

Shared housing represents a paradigm shift from reactive to proactive housing solutions. It leverages existing community assets, reduces public spending, and fosters relational stability. By emphasizing choice, mutual benefit, and cost-sharing, it bypasses the bottlenecks of traditional programs while building human connection and community resilience.

Shared housing offers an inclusive, cost-effective, and empowering response in Camden City, where shelter overflow, voucher shortages, and gentrification threaten housing access. Scaling this model requires bold leadership, collaborative governance, and a name the community can remember. It

must be a movement to ensure no one is left behind simply because they can't afford to live alone.

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Appendices

Appendix A- NASPAA Self-Reflection/Curriculum Evaluation

Appendix B

Fig. B1: Spatial Distribution of Housing Affordability Indicators in Camden County, NJ 2021-2023
 Data Source: Social Explorer American Community Survey (2002-2023)

